

Establishing cut-off points with clinical relevance for bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p21, p27, p53, Sox11 and WT1 in glioblastomas

Emma Camacho-Urkaray¹, Jorge Santos-Juanes², Francisco Borja Gutiérrez-Corres¹, Beatriz García^{3,4}, Luis M. Quirós^{3,4}, Isabel Guerra-Merino¹, José Javier Aguirre¹ and Iván Fernández-Vega^{1,2,4}

- 1- Department of Pathology, Hospital Universitario de Araba-Txagorritxu, Spain.
- 2- Department of Pathology, Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias, Spain.
- 3- Department of Functional Biology, University of Oviedo, Oviedo, Spain.
- 4- Instituto Universitario Fernández-Vega, Oviedo, Spain

Running Head: prognostic markers in glioblastomas

Corresponding author:

Dr. Ivan Fernandez-Vega

Service of Anatomic Pathology, Hospital Universitario de Araba-Txagorritxu,
C/Jose Atxotegui s/n, E-01009, Vitoria-Gasteiz, Alava, Spain

Phone: 34945007001

e-mail: ivan_fernandez_vega@hotmail.com

Word count abstract: 217

Word count main text with references: 3413

Figures: 2

Tables: 2

Supplemental files: none

Acknowledgments: This work was fully supported by Pathology Department at Hospital Universitario de Araba.

Author Contributions: IFV and ECU did the diagnosis of GBM, carried out the TMA preparations and performed the coordination of the study. Immunohistochemistry was done by FBGC. Data analyses were performed by JSJ and JJA. ECU and IFV reviewed the stains, contributed with the data analyses and drafted the manuscript. BG, IGM and LMQ provided technical support and critically reviewed the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest in the research

Establishing cut-off points with clinical relevance for bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p21, p27, p53, Sox11 and WT1 in glioblastomas

Abstract

PURPOSE: To investigate the expression of eight molecules (bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p21, p27, p53, Sox11 and WT1) in glioblastoma (GBM) in order to establish immunohistochemistry cut-off points with clinical relevance.

METHODS: We examined the expression of the proteins in 55 GBM surgical specimens by immunohistochemistry determined using H-score. Immunohistochemistry cut-off points were obtained using Cutoff Finder web platform. Co-expression of biomarkers and correlation with histopathological features were analyzed. Cases were classified according to IDH1 mutation status. Survival curves were also determined.

RESULTS: Correlations for OS were tumour size ($r=-0.278$; $p=0.048$); p53 ($r=-0.452$; $p=0.001$); p16 ($r=0.351$; $p=0.012$) and Sox11 ($r=0.324$; $p=0.020$). Besides, tumour size correlated with cyclin D1 ($r=-0.282$; $p=0.037$); p53 ($r=0.269$; $p=0.041$); Sox11 ($r=-0.309$; $p=0.022$); and WT1 ($r=-0.372$; $p=0.003$). Variables significantly associated with IDH1 mutation status were OS ($p<0.01$), age ($p<0.01$), cyclin D1 ($p=0.046$), p16 ($p=0.019$) and Sox11 ($p=0.012$). Variables significantly associated with worse survival were tumour size $>5\text{cm}$ ($p<0.001$); bcl-2 score >40 points ($p=0.034$); cyclin D1 score ≤ 70 points ($p=0.004$); p16 score ≤ 130 points ($p=0.005$); p53 score >20 points ($p=0.003$), Sox11 score ≤ 40 points ($p<0.001$) and WT1 score ≤ 270 points ($p=0.02$).

CONCLUSIONS: Correlations between proteins and main clinical variables were noted. Finding cut-off points for clinical and molecular variables enables clinicians and pathologists to further understand prognostic values of survival in every cancer.

Key words: glioblastoma; Immunohistochemistry; p53; bcl2; Sox11.

Establishing cut-off points with clinical relevance for bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p21, p27, p53, Sox11 and WT1 in glioblastomas

Introduction

Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is the most common aggressive and treatment refractory malignant brain tumor and despite a few improvements achieved in the last decade, patients generally survive less than one year[1]. Therefore, GBMs are among the most challenging cancers to treat, and there is an urgent need to look for prognostic and diagnostic indicators[2]. Recent cancer genomic studies have revealed an overt complexity of inter-tumour and intra-tumour heterogeneity in GBM, which could explain the heterogeneous clinical outcomes observed[3, 4].

Large families of proteins have been studied during the last years in GBM. One major cause of the resistance to apoptosis in malignant glioma cells is the overexpression of antiapoptotic proteins, including bcl-2, which protects neoplastic cells from toxicity[5]. Therefore, targeting bcl-2 family proteins seems to be a promising therapeutic strategy to combat brain cancer. Moreover, dysregulation of cyclin D1 gene expression or function contributes to the loss of normal cell cycle control during tumorigenesis [6]. Thus, knockdown of cyclin D1 inhibits proliferation, induces apoptosis, and attenuates the invasive capacity of human glioblastoma cells[7]. In addition, the tumour suppression gen p53 and other cell cycle regulator molecules such as p16, p21 and p27 (cell cycle inhibitors) are widely studied biomarkers in human glioma[8]. Nevertheless, due to the numerous cellular processes that are directly or indirectly influenced by these proteins, it often seems that the more we learn about them, the more we appreciate how much remains to be learned[9]. In addition, transcription factors like Sox11 and WT1 are highly specific overexpressed in human malignant gliomas [10, 11]. Sox11 expression was an indicator of favourable prognosis in glioblastomas[12]. However, WT1 is a pleiotropic molecule that appears to function as a context-dependent tumor suppressor or oncogene, and the functional roles in the pathogenesis of glioblastoma have not been extensively studied, although WT1 immunotherapy is considered to be an innovative approach for the treatment of recurrent glioblastoma [13, 14].

It is important to identify prognostic factors for outcome and to tailor adjuvant protocols in accordance with specific biological features of the respective tumor, since there are subpopulations of patients with GBM that differ considerably in their treatment benefit. Thus, a main issue is to study those proteins that normally regulate the pathways of cell proliferation, differentiation, and cell death and whose alterations results in dysregulation of the cell cycle. Then, to improve our understanding of the clinical relevance of these proteins in GBM, we studied the correlation between their immunohistochemically detectable expression and clinical parameters, in order to obtain cut-off points with prognostic relevance that may be used to guide treatment planning.

Materials and methods

Material

The following materials were purchased from the manufacturers indicated: Ultra View universal DAB kit from Roche-Ventana; and the primary antibodies analyzed in the study from Roche-Ventana such as bcl-2 (SP66; rabbit monoclonal antibody), cyclin D1 (SP4-R; rabbit monoclonal antibody), p16 (E6H4; mouse monoclonal antibody), p21 (DCS-60.2; colon monoclonal antibody), p27 (SX53G8; mouse monoclonal antibody), p53 (Bp-53-11; mouse monoclonal antibody), Sox11 (MRQ-58; mouse monoclonal antibody). and WT1 (6F-H2; mouse monoclonal antibody). Mutation of IDH1 was analyzed in these patients by immunohistochemistry for the R132H mutation of IDH1 (DIA-H09; mouse monoclonal antibody) followed by Sanger sequencing. Multiple preliminary assays were done in many human tissues including normal and tumoural specimens in order to validate antibodies as specific, selective, and reproducible.

Patients and samples

Consecutive available samples of 55 GBM were retrieved from Pathology Department of the Hospital Universitario de Araba following approval from the same institute's review board on ethical procedures, and after receiving informed consent from each patient for research on the samples. Patients had a mean age of 62.4yo

and sixty percent of them were males. The mean tumour size was 4.2cm (Table 1). The diagnosis of GBM was based on morphologic criteria according to the most up to-date World Health Organization grading classification (2016) [15]. Tissues obtained from biopsies were fixed in 10% formaldehyde and paraffin embedded then cut into 4µm slices, mounted on treated slides and stained with haematoxylin-eosin (H&E). The normal tissue present in each tissue section was used as a reference.

Tissue microarray construction

Representative tumour regions were identified and selected in each sample for a tissue microarray (TMA) containing three tissue cores from each of 55 GBM. The core diameter was 1.5 mm. After 5 minutes at 60°C the TMA blocks were cut into 4µm thick sections in preparation for immunohistochemistry.

Immunohistochemistry

Paraffin embedded tissue sections were treated with xylene to render them diaphanous (the paraffin being removed later by passing it through decreasing alcohol concentrations until water was reached). Rehydrated sections were rinsed in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) containing 1% tween-20. For the detection of proteins, sections were heated in high pH Envision FLEX target retrieval solution at 65°C for 20 min and then incubated for 20 min at room temperature in the same solution. Endogenous peroxidase activity (3% H₂O₂) and non-specific binding (33% fetal calf serum) were blocked and the sections were incubated overnight at 4°C with the following primary antibodies: bcl-2 (1:200), cyclin D1 (1:200), p16 (1:100), p21 (1:300), p27 (1:200), p53 (1:100), Sox11 (1:200) and WT1 (1:200). Then, Ultra View universal DAB kit was used following the manufacturer's recommendations and using an automated staining procedure. Finally, samples were counterstained with haematoxylin, dehydrated and mounted. The sections were studied and photographed (x20 and x40 objective) under a light microscope with Leica DFC300 FX camera.

Immunohistochemistry assessment

The protein expression levels were evaluated by immunohistochemistry by two independent observers (and a third one in the case of strong disagreement) without any prior knowledge of each patient's clinical information and outcome. We used a semiquantitative approach called H-score (or “histo” score) to analyse every tumor sample as described elsewhere[16, 17]. The final score, ranging from 0 to 300, gives more relative weight to higher-intensity staining in a given tumor sample (Table 1). The sample can then be considered positive or negative on the basis of a specific discriminatory threshold (see below). Strong disagreement was considered for those cases evaluated with more than 30 points of difference.

Statistical analysis

Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients and pathological data were summarized in table 1. All baseline parameters in our series were organized according to IDH1 mutation status (wild type *versus* mutated). To determine a cut-off point in order to stratify any relevant variable into two groups we performed using *Cutoff Finder* (<http://molpath.charite.de/cutoff>). Following a documentation of all cutoff optimization and plot methods that can be found in the *Cutoff Finder* manual, we selected “Survival: significance (log-rank test)” as the method for cutoff determination. Correlations of variables were determined using Spearman correlation test. Categorical data was compared using χ^2 test. To determinate factors associated with worse survival a univariate proportional hazards regression analysis was performed. The Kaplan-Meier method was used to estimate the survival curves, and the comparison between survival functions for different strata was assessed with log-rank tests. All tests were two-sided with p values ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics V22.0 for Windows program.

Results

Protein expressions in normal brain tissue and GBM (Figure 1).

- In normal brain tissue, only p27 showed positive expression in brain cells, mostly in glial cells. However, WT1 showed positive expression in endothelial cells from capillaries. On the contrary, bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p21, p53 and sox11 did not showed positive expression in cerebral tissue.
- Concerning GBM tissue, a different rate of positivity was detected for all proteins. WT1, cyclin D1, p16, and p27 were quantitatively the main proteins expressed in GMB.

Patient demographics and protein expressions analyses in GBM (Table 1).

Fifty-five cases of GBM were divided into two groups depending on their IDH1 mutation status: Immunoreactivity scores for bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p21, p27, p53, Sox11 and WT1 were presented in table 1. WT1 showed the highest mean score while Sox11 was the lowest. The mean score of all proteins were consistently higher in IDH1 mutated group with the exception of p53. Significant differences between groups were noted for overall survival (OS) ($p=0.009$), age ($p<0.001$), cyclin D1 ($p=0.046$), p16 ($p=0.019$) and Sox11 ($p=0.012$).

Co-expression of proteins and clinocopathological parameters

The main variables correlated with OS were tumour size ($r=-0.278$; $p=0.048$); p53 ($r=-0.452$; $p=0.001$); p16 ($r=0.351$; $p=0.012$) and Sox11 ($r=0.324$; $p=0.020$). Besides, tumour size correlated with cyclin D1 ($r=-0.282$; $p=0.037$); p53 ($r=0.269$; $p=0.041$); Sox11 ($r=-0.309$; $p=0.022$); and WT1 ($r=-0.372$; $p=0.006$). Finally, correlation between p53 and WT1 was noted ($r=-0.363$; $p=0.008$).

Univariate proportional-hazards regression analysis of variables included in the study.

In a univariate proportional hazards regression analysis, the protein expressions associated with worse survival were the following: bcl-2 score >40 points ($p=0.034$); cyclin D1 score ≤ 70 points ($p=0.004$); p16 score ≤ 130 points ($p=0.005$); p53 score

>20 points ($p=0.003$); Sox11 score ≤ 40 points ($p<0.001$) and WT1 score ≤ 270 points ($p=0.020$). In addition, univariate analysis confirmed that p21 ($p=0.250$) and p27 ($p=0.978$) results did not affect OS (table 2). Kaplan-Meier curves were shown for those variables associated with survival. The comparison between survival functions for different strata was assessed with log-rank tests (figure 2).

Discussion

This study analyses molecular markers by immunohistochemistry in GBM and shows clear cut-off values significantly relevant for OS. Besides, statistical analysis pointed out the correlation of the expression between some biomarkers like p53, p16 and Sox11 with OS. Of primary importance in the prognosis of GBM is the IDH mutation status. Thus, IDH mutations in GBM were found in general in younger patients and were associated with a better prognosis [18-21]. Besides, GBM with IDH mutations is a very homogeneous molecular group with respect to histological classification, due to most of them belong to the Proneural subtype, based on dominant gene expression patterns[22, 23]. However, recent studies could not demonstrate a higher rate of IDH mutation in the long-term survival group of GBM, highlighting the need to identify other prognostic factors, especially by performing further molecular analysis[24, 25]. In this light, the new challenge in cancer biology is to move from purely morphological classification of tumors to one that is based on molecular criteria.

Our study highlights a generalized increase expression for all proteins in the IDH1 mutated group with the exception of p53 showing a slightly reduction; although significant differences were only noted for cyclin D1, p16 and Sox11. Thus, M Mellai *et al.* described a complementary expression between IDH1 mutation group of GBM and cyclin D1 expression[26]. Although, many studies has pointed out that elevated expression of cyclin D1 in human glioblastoma correlated with poor clinical prognosis, a recently work published by M. Li *et al.*, showed that the expression levels of cyclin D1 were significantly elevated in the Proneural subtype compared to the other subtypes of GBM[27]. But, staining for cycD1 antigen does not necessarily imply that the gene is overexpressed since other molecular mechanisms can also

be responsible for cell cycle deregulation and in many cancers, the impaired ubiquitin-dependent degradation of cyclin D1 is responsible for its elevated levels. Significant differences between groups for p16 could be explained as a positive feedback of the p16/cyclin D1/Rb pathway for the IDH1-mutant group of GBM [28]. Concerning Sox11, it has been described that the Proneural signature of GBM contain several proneural development genes such as SOX genes[29].

Univariate analysis indicated the following immunophenotype as predictor of shorter survival in GBM: bcl-2 score >40 points; cyclin D1 score ≤70 points; p16 score ≤130 points; p53 score >20 points; Sox11 score ≤40 points and WT1 score ≤270 points. The initiation, maintenance, and progression of cancer require the combination of signaling programs that promote cellular proliferation and those that suppress apoptosis. In this sense, previous studies confirmed and extended observations in clinical studies that increased bcl-2 expression correlates with poorer survival[30]. Although elevated cyclin D1 expression in human glioblastoma correlates with poor clinical prognosis, we observed that higher levels of cyclin D1 were present in the IDH1-mutate group of GBM[7, 27]. In addition, gene *p16* encodes a cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor, which functions to regulate cyclin D1, cell cycle progression and malignancies. Thus, p16 inactivation was already described in GBM[31]. In addition, we observed high levels of p16 in the IDH1-mutate group, probably in keeping with a positive feedback of the p16/cyclin D1/Rb pathway previously described[28]. Concerning p53, a negative statistically significant relationship between p53 immunostaining and clinical survival was also observed, suggesting that increased expression of p53 plays an important role in the pathobiology of these tumours[32]. Furthermore, the group of P. Korkolopoulou already highlighted the importance of Sox11 expression as a favourable prognosticator in GBM [12]. Finally, almost 65% of GBM included in this study showed intense and diffuse overexpression for WT1. The remaining 35% GBM with decreased levels of WT1 showed a significantly worse survival. The functional roles of WT1 in GBM pathogenesis remain controversial, with WT1 being involved in regulating cell proliferation and apoptosis in at least some GBM[33]. It is noteworthy to mention that immunotherapy targeting WT1 has proven

to be effective in recurrent GBM suggesting that this approach may be an important new treatment modality for the disease[11, 14, 34].

Eventually, the integration of tissue markers to help inform clinical decision-making has been successfully used in multiple malignancies. In order to translate a continuous variable into a clinical decision, it is necessary to determine a cutoff point and to stratify variables into two group. Remarkably, we describe for the first time cut-off values for those molecules that showed clinical relevance in GBM. However, cutoffs are often chosen as median or mean value of the biomarker or adjusted manually. Thus, we used a comprehensive and straightforward online tool for cut-off point optimization that can help to improve the quality of biomarker studies.

Conclusion

In summary, this study does present compelling evidence that establishing “cut-off points” by immunohistochemistry for any of the above antigens would contribute to increase the prognostic information also provided by currently available ancillary studies used in the routine pathological evaluation of the gliomas. Thus, we described a significant progress in the understanding of establishing clear cut-off points in order to stratify patients into two groups with different OS, therefore each probably requiring a diverse treatment.

Finally, our study suffers from the same limitations as other retrospective studies, with a biased selection of tissue for building TMA of GBM, which influences the results. Besides, an important issue is that any study attempting to establish cut-offs for immunohistochemical expression is fraught with the problem of inter-laboratory variation. However, one of the strengths of the present study is that we had a larger cohort of uniformly GBM tumours. Otherwise, further controlled studies are needed to validate our results in a prospective study with a greater number of GBM patients.

References

- 1 B. Tran and M.A. Rosenthal, *Journal of clinical neuroscience : official journal of the Neurosurgical Society of Australasia* 17, 417-421 (2010) doi: 10.1016/j.jocn.2009.09.004
- 2 M. Touat, A. Idbah, M. Sanson and K.L. Ligon, *Annals of oncology : official journal of the European Society for Medical Oncology* 28, 1457-1472 (2017) doi: 10.1093/annonc/mdx106
- 3 R. Fisher, L. Puztai and C. Swanton, *British journal of cancer* 108, 479-485 (2013) doi: 10.1038/bjc.2012.581
- 4 H. Ohgaki and P. Kleihues, *Acta neuropathologica* 109, 93-108 (2005) doi: 10.1007/s00401-005-0991-y
- 5 K.E. Tagscherer, A. Fassel, B. Campos, M. Farhadi, A. Kraemer, B.C. Bock, S. Macher-Goeppinger, B. Radlwimmer, O.D. Wiestler, C. Herold-Mende and W. Roth, *Oncogene* 27, 6646-6656 (2008) doi: 10.1038/onc.2008.259
- 6 M.C. Casimiro, M. Crosariol, E. Loro, Z. Li and R.G. Pestell, *Genes & cancer* 3, 649-657 (2012) doi: 10.1177/1947601913479022
- 7 J. Wang, Q. Wang, Y. Cui, Z.Y. Liu, W. Zhao, C.L. Wang, Y. Dong, L. Hou, G. Hu, C. Luo, J. Chen and Y. Lu, *Journal of neuro-oncology* 106, 473-484 (2012) doi: 10.1007/s11060-011-0692-4
- 8 Y. Jin, W. Xiao, T. Song, G. Feng and Z. Dai, *Neurochemical research* 41, 1723-1731 (2016) doi: 10.1007/s11064-016-1888-y
- 9 C.D. James, *Neuro-oncology* 12, 421 (2010) doi: 10.1093/neuonc/noq037
- 10 B. Weigle, R. Ebner, A. Temme, S. Schwind, M. Schmitz, A. Kiessling, M.A. Rieger, G. Schackert, H.K. Schackert and E.P. Rieber, *Oncology reports* 13, 139-144 (2005)
- 11 Y. Nakahara, H. Okamoto, T. Mineta and K. Tabuchi, *Brain tumor pathology* 21, 113-116 (2004)
- 12 P. Korkolopoulou, G. Levidou, E.A. El-Habr, C. Adamopoulos, P. Fragkou, E. Boviatsis, M.S. Themistocleous, K. Petraki, G. Vrettakos, M. Sakalidou, V. Samaras, A. Zisakis, A. Saetta, I. Chatziandreu, E. Patsouris and C. Piperi, *British journal of cancer* 108, 2142-2152 (2013) doi: 10.1038/bjc.2013.176

- 13 N. Hashimoto, *Neurologia medico-chirurgica* 56, 355-360 (2016) doi: 10.2176/nmc.ra.2015-0310
- 14 Y. Chiba, N. Hashimoto, A. Tsuboi, C. Rabo, Y. Oka, M. Kinoshita, N. Kagawa, Y. Oji, H. Sugiyama and T. Yoshimine, *Brain tumor pathology* 27, 29-34 (2010) doi: 10.1007/s10014-010-0265-9
- 15 D.N. Louis, A. Perry, G. Reifenberger, A. von Deimling, D. Figarella-Branger, W.K. Cavenee, H. Ohgaki, O.D. Wiestler, P. Kleihues and D.W. Ellison, *Acta neuropathologica* 131, 803-820 (2016) doi: 10.1007/s00401-016-1545-1
- 16 J. Mazieres, W. Brugger, F. Cappuzzo, P. Middel, A. Frosch, I. Bara, G. Klingelschmitt and B. Klughammer, *Lung cancer* 82, 231-237 (2013) doi: 10.1016/j.lungcan.2013.07.016
- 17 F.R. Hirsch, M. Varella-Garcia, P.A. Bunn, Jr., M.V. Di Maria, R. Veve, R.M. Bremmes, A.E. Baron, C. Zeng and W.A. Franklin, *Journal of clinical oncology : official journal of the American Society of Clinical Oncology* 21, 3798-3807 (2003) doi: 10.1200/JCO.2003.11.069
- 18 H. Yan, D.W. Parsons, G. Jin, R. McLendon, B.A. Rasheed, W. Yuan, I. Kos, I. Batinic-Haberle, S. Jones, G.J. Riggins, H. Friedman, A. Friedman, D. Reardon, J. Herndon, K.W. Kinzler, V.E. Velculescu, B. Vogelstein and D.D. Bigner, *The New England journal of medicine* 360, 765-773 (2009) doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa0808710
- 19 S. Nobusawa, T. Watanabe, P. Kleihues and H. Ohgaki, *Clinical Cancer Research* 15, 6002-6007 (2009) doi: 10.1158/1078-0432.ccr-09-0715
- 20 M. Sanson, Y. Marie, S. Paris, A. Idbaih, J. Laffaire, F. Ducray, S. El Hallani, B. Boisselier, K. Mokhtari, K. Hoang-Xuan and J.Y. Delattre, *Journal of clinical oncology : official journal of the American Society of Clinical Oncology* 27, 4150-4154 (2009) doi: 10.1200/JCO.2009.21.9832
- 21 H. Ohgaki, P. Dessen, B. Jourde, S. Horstmann, T. Nishikawa, P.L. Di Patre, C. Burkhard, D. Schuler, N.M. Probst-Hensch, P.C. Maiorka, N. Baeza, P. Pisani, Y. Yonekawa, M.G. Yasargil, U.M. Lutolf and P. Kleihues, *Cancer research* 64, 6892-6899 (2004) doi: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-04-1337

- 22 R.G. Verhaak, K.A. Hoadley, E. Purdom, V. Wang, Y. Qi, M.D. Wilkerson, C.R. Miller, L. Ding, T. Golub, J.P. Mesirov, G. Alexe, M. Lawrence, M. O'Kelly, P. Tamayo, B.A. Weir, S. Gabriel, W. Winckler, S. Gupta, L. Jakkula, H.S. Feiler, J.G. Hodgson, C.D. James, J.N. Sarkaria, C. Brennan, A. Kahn, P.T. Spellman, R.K. Wilson, T.P. Speed, J.W. Gray, M. Meyerson, G. Getz, C.M. Perou, D.N. Hayes and N. Cancer Genome Atlas Research, *Cancer cell* 17, 98-110 (2010) doi: 10.1016/j.ccr.2009.12.020
- 23 A. Cohen, S. Holmen and H. Colman, *Current neurology and neuroscience reports* 13, 345-345 (2013) doi: 10.1007/s11910-013-0345-4
- 24 A. Amelot, P. De Cremoux, V. Quillien, M. Polivka, H. Adle-Biassette, J. Lehmann-Che, L. Françoise, A.F. Carpentier, B. George, E. Mandonnet and S. Froelich, *PloS one* 10, e0130596 (2015) doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0130596
- 25 R.J. Molenaar, D. Verbaan, S. Lamba, C. Zanon, J.W.M. Jeuken, S.H.E. Boots-Sprenger, P. Wesseling, T.J.M. Hulsebos, D. Troost, A.A. van Tilborg, S. Leenstra, W.P. Vandertop, A. Bardelli, C.J.F. van Noorden and F.E. Bleeker, *Neuro-oncology* 16, 1263-1273 (2014) doi: 10.1093/neuonc/nou005
- 26 M. Mellai, A. Piazzzi, V. Caldera, O. Monzeglio, P. Cassoni, G. Valente and D. Schiffer, *Journal of neuro-oncology* 105, 345 (2011) doi: 10.1007/s11060-011-0596-3
- 27 A.X. Ming Li, Desiree Floyd, Inan Olmez, Jeongwu Lee, Jakub Godlewski, Agnieszka Bronisz, Krishna P.L. Bhat, Erik P. Sulman, Ichiro Nakano and Benjamin Purow, *Oncotarget* 8, 12 (2017)
- 28 B. Schwartz, C. Avivi-Green and S. Polak-Charcon, *Molecular and cellular biochemistry* 188, 21-30 (1998)
- 29 H.S. Phillips, S. Kharbanda, R. Chen, W.F. Forrest, R.H. Soriano, T.D. Wu, A. Misra, J.M. Nigro, H. Colman, L. Soroceanu, P.M. Williams, Z. Modrusan, B.G. Feuerstein and K. Aldape, *Cancer cell* 9, 157-173 doi: 10.1016/j.ccr.2006.02.019
- 30 T.A. Doucette and G. Rao, *Clinical neurosurgery* 58, 149-154 (2011)
- 31 S.S. C Romagosa, L López-Vicente, A Mazo, M E Lleonart, J Castellvi and S Ramon y Cajal, *Oncogene*, 10 (2011)

- 32 F.S. Pardo, D.W. Hsu, R. Zeheb, J.T. Efird, P.G. Okunieff and D.M. Malkin, *British journal of cancer* 91, 1678-1686 (2004)
- 33 N. Kijima, N. Hosen, N. Kagawa, N. Hashimoto, M. Kinoshita, Y. Oji, H. Sugiyama and T. Yoshimine, *Anticancer research* 34, 61-67 (2014)
- 34 S. Izumoto, A. Tsuboi, Y. Oka, T. Suzuki, T. Hashiba, N. Kagawa, N. Hashimoto, M. Maruno, O.A. Elisseeva, T. Shirakata, M. Kawakami, Y. Oji, S. Nishida, S. Ohno, I. Kawase, J. Hatazawa, S. Nakatsuka, K. Aozasa, S. Morita, J. Sakamoto, H. Sugiyama and T. Yoshimine, *Journal of neurosurgery* 108, 963-971 (2008) doi: 10.3171/JNS/2008/108/5/0963

Figure legends

Figure 1. Immunostaining for bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p21, p27, p53, Sox11 and WT1 in normal brain tissue and GBM. (A, B) Bcl-2 expression in normal (A) and GBM (B). **(C, D)** Cyclin D1 expression in normal (C) and GBM (D). **(E, F)** P16 expression in normal (E) and GBM (F). **(G, H)** P21 expression in normal (G) and GBM (H). **(I, J)** P27 expression in normal (I) and GBM (J). **(K, L)** P53 expression in normal (K) and GBM (L). **(M, N)** WT1 expression in normal (M) and GBM (N). (O, P) Sox11 expression in normal (O) and GBM (P). Magnification x400.

Figure 2. Kaplan-Meier overall survival curves of the series of 55 GBM for bcl-2, cyclin D1, p16, p53, Sox11 and WT1.

Table 1: Demographic data and protein expression related to IDH1 status of 55 GBM cases.

	TOTAL CASES 55(100%) Mean, cases (%)	IDH1 wt 43(78%) Mean, cases (%)	IDH1 mut 12(22%) Mean, cases (%)	<i>p-value</i>
OS (weeks)	46.4	38.4	73.8	
≤52	35 (64)	31 (72)	4 (33)	0.009
>52	20 (36)	12 (28)	8 (67)	
Age, years	62.4	66.3	51.2	
≤55	12 (22)	4 (9)	8 (67)	<0.001
>55	43(78)	39 (91)	4 (33)	
Tumour size	4.2	4.3	4.1	
≤5cm	36 (65)	28 (65)	8 (67)	0.920
>5cm	19 (35)	15 (35)	4 (33)	
Gender				
Male	33 (60)	27 (63)	6 (50)	0.424
Female	22 (40)	16 (37)	6 (50)	
Bcl-2	46.2	49.7	35.1	
≤40	37 (67)	27 (63)	10 (83)	0.210
>40	18 (33)	16 (37)	2 (17)	
Cyclin D1	87.9	72.6	143.6	
≤70	23 (42)	21 (49)	2 (17)	0.046
>70	32 (58)	22 (51)	10 (83)	
p16	121.9	98.4	205.1	
≤130	34 (62)	30 (70)	4 (33)	0.019
>130	21 (38)	13 (30)	8 (67)	
p21	47.9	44.8	63.1	
≤50	36 (65)	30 (70)	6 (50)	0.184
>50	19 (35)	13 (30)	6 (50)	
p27	117.4	114.1	129.9	
≤70	36 (65)	28 (65)	8 (67)	0.920
>70	19 (35)	15 (35)	4 (33)	
p53	70.6	73.2	62.1	
≤20	18 (33)	12 (28)	6 (50)	0.162
>20	37 (67)	31 (72)	6 (50)	
Sox11	34.1	29.4	52.7	
≤40	39 (71)	34 (79)	5 (42)	0.012
>40	16 (29)	9(21)	7 (58)	
WT1	227.9	225.4	239.6	
≤270	23 (42)	19 (44)	4 (33)	0.554
>270	32 (58)	24 (56)	8 (67)	

wt: wild type; mut; mutant

Table 2: Univariate analyses of variables associated with survival

Variables	Univariate analysis		
	HR	95% CI	p value
Age, years (≤ 52 vs. > 52)	1.407	0.699-2.833	0.339
Gender (male vs. female)	0.809	0.454-1.442	0.437
Tumour size (≤ 5 cm vs > 5 cm)	3.949	2.032-7.673	<0.001
Bcl-2, score (≤ 40 vs > 40)	1.967	1.052-3.678	0.034
Cyclin D1, score (≤ 70 vs > 70)	0.411	0.224-0.756	0.004
p16, score (≤ 130 vs > 130)	0.401	0.213-0.757	0.005
p21, score (≤ 50 vs > 50)	0.697	0.377-1.289	0.250
p27, score (≤ 70 vs > 70)	1.008	0.559-1.819	0.978
p53, score (≤ 20 vs > 20)	2.739	1.06-5.337	0.003
Sox11, score (≤ 40 vs > 40)	0.269	0.130-0.556	<0.001
WT1, score (≤ 270 vs > 270)	0.498	0.276-0.897	0.020

Cox regression model. CI – confidence interval, HR – hazard ratio,

colour figure 1

